
**Department of
Psychology**

Rethinking Special Educational Needs and Disabilities

Main Report: May 2026

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Executive Summary

This project examined how special educational needs and disabilities (SEND) emerge, cluster, and change from early childhood to adolescence. Currently, SEND identification varies across schools and local authorities; support is typically triggered once needs become visible in the classroom, rather than when they begin to develop.

We accessed longitudinal data from approximately 50,000 children and young people who took part in one of four research studies: the [Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children](#); the [British Cohort Study](#); the [Millennium Cohort Study](#); and the [Twins Early Development Study](#). The children and young people were followed from birth until late adolescence (and beyond). We used data collected in early childhood (age 3-5 years), middle childhood (age 7-10 years), and early adolescence (age 11-14 years) as predictors and data collected in mid-adolescence (age 17 years), late adolescence (age 21 years), and early adulthood (age 24-29 years) as outcomes.

We used two complementary approaches to analyse the data: one to map which needs commonly occur; the other to identify groups of children and young people who share similar clusters of need. We used genetic data from both parents and their child to understand how genetic and environmental influences affect development from early childhood to adolescence. The research project was co-produced with children and young people with SEND, their parents, and education professionals.

Identifying SEND

Our work demonstrates that children and young people's needs manifest across three interconnected areas of development. These are: 1) cognition and language, 2) social functioning, and 3) emotional functioning¹. However, difficulties do not occur in isolation; needs in one area of development often co-occur with needs in another area of development.

Policy Recommendation. We recommend that the SEND Code of Practice (2014) be updated so that the current 'areas of need' are replaced with the following 'areas of development': 1) cognition and language, 2) social functioning, and 3) emotional functioning². 'Communication and interaction' should be removed as a

¹ Social and emotional functioning cluster together in early and middle childhood. The two areas of development separate into two distinct areas of development in adolescence.

² We did not test sensory and physical needs in our analysis due to limitations around data availability.

separate area of need since this conflates two areas of development that are distinct (language and social functioning).

Alignment with Schools White Paper. Our areas of development are slightly different to the ones recommended in the Schools White Paper (2026) in two key respects. First, our proposal includes grouping ‘cognition and language’ whereas the Schools White Paper (2026) separates this into ‘executive function’ and ‘speech, language, and communication needs’. There are good theoretical and practical reasons to separate these two, but our work demonstrates that they are closely interrelated in development. Second, our proposal is to separate social and emotional functioning, at the very least in adolescence, whereas the Schools White Paper (2026) keeps these two areas of need paired together. Our data analysis aligns well with previous research, theory, and lived experiences of children and young people; social and emotional functioning should be considered separate, but related, areas of development.

Needs within areas of development are especially closely related. For example, a child or young person who struggles with reading is also likely to struggle with using language in conversation, while a child or young person who has difficulties with social skills is also likely to struggle forming friendships. Recognising these patterns will help schools identify children and young people’s needs earlier and more accurately.

Practice Recommendation. When a child or young person is identified as having a need, schools should work on the assumption that they are likely to experience other needs within the same area of development.

Needs within the same area of development are especially connected but there are also connections between needs in different areas of development; that is, a need in one area of development might co-occur with a need in another area of development. For example, cognitive and language needs might co-occur with emotional needs. Recognising the interconnected nature of development is crucial for understanding children and young people’s profiles of strengths and challenges.

Policy Recommendation. The policy that requires schools to record SEND as primary and secondary types should be scrapped. Instead, all of a child or young person's needs should be recorded across each area of development so that each child or young person has a full profile of needs. This approach aligns better with the reality that most children and young people have needs across multiple areas of development.

Alignment with Schools White Paper. This recommendation aligns well with the 'individual support plans' suggested in the Schools White Paper (2026). Instead of recording primary and second SEND types, children and young people's full profile of needs can be recorded in the proposed 'individual support plans', which will be created for all children and young people with SEND.

Through our engagement with children and young people with SEND, their parents, and education professionals, as well as our knowledge of the research literature, we identified a set of variables available in the survey datasets which denote needs that likely underpin learning and engagement in education to include in our analysis.

Policy Recommendation. The 'need types' in the SEND Code of Practice (2014) should be renamed 'developmental needs'. This captures that these needs arise within 'areas of development'. A list of the developmental needs we used in our analysis is presented in Table 1 (at the end of the Executive Summary), though this was partly based on data availability and should not be taken as definitive.

Alignment with Schools White Paper. There is good overlap between the developmental needs, clustered under areas of development, that we used in our analysis (described in Table 1) and those outlined in the Schools White Paper (2026). We suggest that the two lists of needs are merged to create a comprehensive list of needs to be used by schools.

Official SEND statistics are biased by inconsistencies in SEND identification (Hutchinson et al., 2025). Based on our statistical modelling of research data, we estimate that between 20-30% of children and young people in England have developmental needs. This is higher than the c.20% formally identified as having SEND.

There are some differences in methodology that make direct comparisons between our estimate and official SEND identification rates difficult: 1) we mapped developmental needs between the ages of 3-14 years whereas official SEND estimates are based on ages 5-16 years; 2) we did not include sensory and physical needs in our analysis; 3) children and young people with the most severe needs are unlikely to be part of large research studies as they would be unable to complete the measures. This means our estimate is almost certainly conservative. This is in line with other parts of our analysis which suggest that many children and young people with developmental needs are not being identified as having SEND.

Policy Recommendation. The Government should plan and budget for supporting a higher level of developmental needs than is currently reported by official SEND statistics.

Supporting SEND

Our findings provide insights into how support for children and young people with SEND should be designed and delivered across different stages of development from early childhood (age 3-5 years) to middle childhood (age 7-10 years) and then in adolescence (age 11-14 years).

Developmental needs that appear to be similar might arise from different underlying causes. The interconnected nature of various developmental needs indicates that there is unlikely to be a single cause for a given need. For example, reading difficulty in two children might be caused by separate processes; these two children will likely require different types of intervention.

Practice Recommendation. Support should be planned based on the full profile of a child or young person's strengths and challenges. This will give practitioners the best chance of targeting the cause(s) of the needs.

Alignment with Schools White Paper. Recording all needs in the proposed 'individual support plan' for all children and young people with SEND will allow for support to be planned with their full range of needs in mind.

Our statistical modelling revealed that children and young people's needs form clusters that do not map onto existing diagnostic (e.g. 'autism spectrum disorder') or educational (e.g. 'specific learning difficulty') labels. This means that some children and young people struggle in education despite not meeting any SEND diagnostic criteria.

Practice Recommendation. Access to support should be needs based and not dependent on diagnostic assessments, as many children and young people will not meet diagnostic assessment criteria and still have needs.

Alignment with Schools White Paper. The above practice recommendation aligns with the Schools White Paper (2026), which recognises that diagnostic and bureaucratic processes often get in the way of supporting children and young people with SEND. Our analysis supports this sentiment; we echo that support for SEND should be based on need and not dependent upon diagnostic assessment.

Our work does not support the Government's proposal of approximately seven specialist provision packages. Our analysis demonstrates that children and young

people's needs cannot be reduced to a handful of needs profiles. Off the shelf specialist provision packages will inevitably leave some children and young people without the support they need. Instead, support should be focussed truly on individual needs.

We also examined how genetic and environmental influences on developmental skills change from early childhood to adolescence.

In the early years, children's skills can shift rapidly, as their development is highly malleable and shaped by their environments and experiences. While some children, particularly those with more complex or global needs, may be identified and supported before school, not all children access or are identified as having SEND through pre-school provision.

By primary school, children's strengths and challenges are typically more clearly expressed, making this a critical point at which needs can be more consistently identified and appropriate support put in place.

Practice Recommendation. Screening for a broad range of needs should be undertaken at the beginning of primary school (e.g., in reception) and then again part-way through primary school.

By adolescence, social and emotional functioning become more independent of each other; emotional difficulties may not be as closely related to social difficulties in adolescence compared to childhood (and vice versa).

Practice Recommendation. Screening for social and emotional needs should be undertaken around the beginning of secondary school.

In adolescence, young people's strengths and challenges are more established; Whilst genetic influences still only play a small role in shaping young people's developmental skills in adolescence, they are stronger in adolescence than in childhood.

Policy Recommendation. The education system should offer genuinely diverse pathways- academic, vocational, creative, technical, and preparing for adult life- so that young people can progress in ways that align with their developmental needs and genetic propensities.

Alignment with Schools White Paper. There is some indication that the above policy recommendation is given consideration in the Schools White Paper (2026).

The proposal to diversify the Progress 8 measure to include a broader mix of subjects is a step in the right direction. We encourage the Government to go further and offer more diverse pathways much earlier in secondary school and recognise that some children and young people with SEND need more time to reach a certain level of attainment or different types of qualifications.

Together, our findings provide a coherent, developmentally informed theoretical framework for improving SEND identification and support, one that reflects how children and young people develop, how needs cluster, and how support should be adapted across the school years.

Table 1. Proposed Areas of Development and Developmental Needs³

Cognition and Language	Social Functioning	Emotional Functioning	Sensory and/or Physical Needs
Using language in conversation	Behavioural regulation	Regulating emotions	N/A ⁴
Understanding others	Forming and maintaining relationships	Self-esteem	
Cognitive flexibility	Navigating social conflict	Positive affect	
Reading	Working collaboratively with others	Low mood	
Spelling	Using language in social situations		
Writing	Understanding others		
Mathematics	Navigating social interactions		
Working memory			
Managing impulses			
Attention			
Risk taking			
Planning and decision making			
Processing information			

³ Through our engagement with children and young people with SEND, their parents, and education professionals, as well as our knowledge of the research literature, we identified a set of variables available in the survey datasets; we translated these variables to developmental needs and include them here.

⁴ We did not investigate sensory and physical needs due to the lack of available data in the datasets. Therefore, we cannot make recommendations on these types of needs.

Context and Brief Literature Review

Children and young people (CYP) with special educational needs and disabilities (SEND) make up approximately a fifth of all CYP in England (Department for Education, 2025). This has increased by 35% in the last decade. A CYP with SEND has significantly greater difficulty in learning than the majority of others of the same age, or has a disability which prevents or hinders them from making use of educational facilities (Department for Education & Department of Health: SEND Code of Practice 2014). CYP with SEND whose needs cannot be met by ordinarily available provision are entitled to an Education, Health, and Care Plan (EHCP), which is a legally binding document outlining the CYP's needs and required additional provision. Approximately 5% of CYP in England have an EHCP (Department for Education, 2025); this represents an increase of nearly 90% over the last decade (Department for Education, 2025) and the proportion is projected to continue to increase in the short term and fall back to current levels over the next decade (Department for Education: Schools White Paper, 2026).

Schools in England group SEND into four broad areas of need: 1) communication and interaction; 2) cognition and learning; 3) social, emotional and mental health; 4) sensory and/or physical (Department for Education & Department of Health: SEND Code of Practice 2014). Within these broad areas of need, CYP are assigned one or two specific types of need, which may be a diagnostic label (e.g., autism spectrum disorder) or an educational descriptor (e.g., specific learning difficulty). There are 12 types of need in total⁵, which are intended to guide schools in understanding a CYP's profile and determining appropriate support.

In practice, all CYP with SEND are assigned a primary SEND type and some are also assigned a secondary SEND type. Many CYP have multiple needs that cannot be reduced to one or two labels. Furthermore, the SEND types may change over time (e.g., a speech, language, and communication need in primary school may change to a social, emotional, and mental health difficulty in secondary school). Additionally, a CYP's SEND types may cut across a range of different areas of need (e.g., a child or young person may have one need in 'communication and interaction' and another in 'social, emotional, and mental health').

The problem with the SEND types is that they do not adequately describe what challenges a CYP is experiencing with learning and education. Two CYP with the same SEND type might have a different set of needs. For example, two CYP

⁵ **Communication and Interaction:** speech, language, and communication needs, autism spectrum disorder. **Cognition and Learning:** specific learning difficulty, moderate learning difficulty, severe learning difficulty, profound and multiple learning difficulty. **Social, Emotional and Mental Health:** this is both an area of need and type of need. **Sensory and/or Physical:** visual impairment, hearing impairment, multi-sensory impairment, physical disability. **Other Difficulty/Disability** (CYP's needs does not fit one of the above categories).

whose SEND type is listed as ‘autism spectrum disorder’ may well experience different challenges; for example, CYP A may have typical cognitive skills but experience social difficulties, whilst CYP B may be minimally verbal with intellectual impairment. By the same token, a similar set of challenges might manifest across different need types; two CYP with the same needs might have a different SEND type. For example, CYP C, who has a speech, language and communication need, might struggle with working memory, whilst CYP D, who has a specific learning difficulty, might also struggle with working memory. SEND types do not describe underlying needs.

There are also a number of issues which limit our understanding of the level of need across the population in England. Previous work funded by the Nuffield Foundation investigated how societal factors (e.g., schools, neighbourhoods) affect CYPs’ likelihood of being identified with SEND (Hutchinson et al, 2025). Widespread inequalities in SEND identification were reported; the authors describe this as a ‘postcode lottery’. Such inequalities mean that CYP who likely do have a SEND are not being identified and therefore miss out on the support that they need. This means that the official estimates of SEND, those produced annually by the Department for Education, are biased by inequalities in identification.

We sought to address these problems by adopting a data driven approach to understanding CYPs’ strengths and challenges during childhood and adolescence. We adopted a transdiagnostic approach, focussing on measures of CYPs’ strengths and challenges beyond SEND labels and diagnostic processes. Rather than focussing on CYP whose SEND had been identified, we focussed on all CYP irrespective of whether they had been identified with SEND or not to estimate the level of need across the population. We were not the first to adopt such a transdiagnostic approach to SEND (see Astle et al., 2021 for a brief overview). However, previous transdiagnostic investigations of SEND were limited for a number of reasons.

First, they considered ‘communication and interaction’ and ‘cognition and learning’ separately from ‘social, emotional, and mental health difficulties’. This is problematic because CYP with ‘communication and interaction’ or ‘cognition and learning’ difficulties are more likely to experience ‘social, emotional, and mental health’ difficulties (e.g., van Steensel et al., 2011, Conti-Ramsden et al., 2019). This may be due to shared underlying cognitive profiles (Snyder et al., 2015), environmental risk (Toseeb et al., 2020), or genetic influences (Toseeb et al., 2022). Therefore, we considered needs that underpin ‘communication and interaction’, ‘cognition and learning’, and ‘social, emotional, and mental health difficulties’ together to determine the patterns of co-occurrence.

Second, previous transdiagnostic investigations of SEND typically focussed on one developmental period, either early childhood, middle childhood, or adolescence. This is problematic because different types of need likely reciprocally influence each other as a CYP develops. This can be conceptualised through the developmental cascades framework (Masten & Cicchetti, 2010), which suggests that early experiences in one area of development (e.g., cognition) can affect another

area of development (e.g., social skills). Additionally, some needs first manifest during specific periods of risk. For example, early adolescence is a particularly sensitive period for the onset of mental health difficulties, with half of all lifetime mental health conditions emerging before the age of 14 years (Kessler et al., 2005). Therefore, we considered a range of needs that likely underpin SEND across three developmental stages: early childhood (age 3-5 years), middle childhood (age 7-10 years), and adolescence (age 11-14 years).

Finally, previous transdiagnostic investigations used opportunistic samples that are not representative of the population of England. For CYP to be part of a study of SEND, typically one or more of the following conditions needs to be met: 1) they have an identified SEND, 2) a parent considers they are struggling at school, 3) a teacher thinks they are struggling at school, or 4) they are accessing professional support (e.g., speech and language therapy). This is problematic because inequalities exist in all of these referral routes leading to referral bias. Therefore, any study of SEND relying on opportunistic samples will likely be biased by these inequalities. Additionally, research focussing solely on those identified with SEND tells us very little about what CYPs' development looks like at the population level; to understand atypical development we need to understand what typical development looks like. This is particularly relevant to SEND because CYPs' SEND in England are defined relative to others of the same age (Department for Education & Department of Health: SEND Code of Practice, 2014). Therefore, we included in our investigation samples of CYP with SEND and those without SEND who were part of ongoing longitudinal research studies intended to be representative of the population or at least geographic communities within the population.

Even if/when issues of identification and conceptualisation are resolved, it remains unclear how early intervention and support can be targeted. It is well documented that a poor early home environment is associated with educational disadvantage at school-entry (Roulstone et al., 2011). What remains unclear is whether this relationship is causal. That is, does a positive early home environment lead to fewer challenges in education and learning? Or could there be other explanations for the correlation?

This ambiguity can be understood through the framework of gene-environment correlation, which highlights how genetic propensities and environmental experiences are intertwined. Typically, such gene-environment correlations are conceptualised in three ways. First, passive gene-environment correlation occurs when parents transmit both genes and environments to their children; for example, highly educated parents may pass on genetic propensity associated with cognitive ability while also providing a home rich in books and learning resources. Second, evocative gene-environment correlation refers to the way children's genetically influenced characteristics elicit particular responses from others; for instance, a child who talks well from an early age may naturally get more conversation, encouragement, and attention from parents, caregivers, and teachers. Third, and in contrast, active gene-environment correlation involves individuals selecting or shaping environments that align with their genetic tendencies, such as a

child with a natural interest in reading choosing to spend more time reading books or more time at the library. Together, these processes make it difficult to disentangle whether early home environments causally influence educational disadvantage or instead reflect underlying genetic influences.

To begin to tease apart these possibilities, we used an approach that looks at CYPs' strengths and challenges alongside both their own genetic tendencies and those of their parents, with a particular focus on passive gene-environment correlation. In particular, we considered the CYPs' strengths and challenges, their genetic tendencies, and their parents' genetic tendencies. This allows us to capture what is sometimes called genetic nurture. That is, how parents can shape the home environment independently of the genetic tendency that they pass on to their child. By looking at all of these factors together, we can better separate the influence of the CYPs' own genetics from the ways parents shape the environment, and gain a clearer sense of whether less stimulating early home environments might be driving educational disadvantage.

Research Aims and Objectives

The aim of this project was to lead a fundamental rethink of SEND identification and support. We provide a novel theoretical framework for labelling SEND in schools by focusing on underlying strengths and challenges. To do this, we addressed research questions in three work packages:

1. We explored how language, learning, cognition, social, emotional, and mental health difficulties cluster in the general population and whether these clusters are similar or different in early childhood (age 3-5 years), middle childhood (age 7-10 years), and adolescence (age 11-14 years).
2. We identified sub-groups of CYP with similar profiles of strengths and challenges based on the clusters identified, and compared them to existing SEND types. Specifically, we asked:
 - a. How many sub-groups of CYP with similar profiles of need exist in the general population?
 - b. What is the overall level of developmental need in England?
 - c. Do the data-derived sub-groups of developmental need correspond to SEND types used in schools?
 - d. How do the data-derived sub-groups of developmental need compare to SEND labels used in schools at predicting outcomes later in adolescence and young adulthood?
3. Finally, we mapped the influence of intergenerational risk through genetic and environmental pathways to children's strengths and challenges. Specifically, we asked: how and to what extent is risk for social, emotional, and cognitive difficulties transmitted from parents to children.

Methods

Datasets

The project involved secondary analysis of existing data. We used data from four population-based birth cohorts in England: the Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC, n=15,645; Boyd et al., 2013; Fraser et al., 2013); the Millennium Cohort Study (MCS, n=18,827; University College London, 2024); the Twins Early Development Study (TEDS, n=7,859; Lockhart et al., 2023); and the British Cohort Study (BCS, n=12,509; Sullivan et al., 2022). The combined sample size was approximately 50,000 CYP.

Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC)

Pregnant women resident in Avon, UK with expected dates of delivery between 1st April 1991 and 31st December 1992 were invited to take part in the study. The initial number of pregnancies enrolled was 14,541 and 13,988 children were alive at 1 year of age. Mothers and children have been followed up at various points over the past 35 years. We used data from various data collected from early childhood (3 years) to adulthood (29 years). The study website contains details of all the data that is available through a fully searchable data dictionary and variable search tool: <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/alspac/researchers/our-data/>.

British Cohort Study (BCS)

The 1970 British Cohort Study (BCS70) is an ongoing, multidisciplinary, longitudinal study of a cohort of over 17,000 individuals born in England, Scotland and Wales. The initial sample comprised all births in Britain in a single week in 1970. Participants have been followed up at multiple points throughout life. We used data collected at multiple time points between early childhood (age 3 years) and adolescence (18 years).

Millennium Cohort Study (MCS)

The MCS is a UK based nationally representative birth-cohort study with an original sample of approximately 19,000 children born between 2000 and 2002 in the four nations of the UK (England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland). Families were recruited to the study when the young person was 9 months old and followed-up at ages 3, 5, 7, 11, 14, 17, and 23 years. Parents completed questionnaires about themselves and their child and, when the young people were able to, they completed questionnaires and in-clinic assessments. We used data from all time points between early childhood (age 3 years) and adolescence (17 years).

Twins Early Development Study (TEDS)

TEDS is a longitudinal twin cohort study of children born in England and Wales between 1994 and 1996. Nearly 14,000 families took part in the first wave of data collection when the twins were 18 months old. Subsets of the original sample were invited to take part in subsequent waves. At the time of recruitment, the sample was representative of the UK population. We used data from one twin per family at multiple time points between early childhood (age 3 years) and early adulthood (age 26 years).

Sample Demographics

In all datasets, we focused on CYP from England only. Approximately 50% of the samples were male (49-52%), and most were of white ethnicity (73-96%). Participants had a range of socioeconomic and ethnic backgrounds. The samples included CYP born in the 1970s, 1990s, and 2000s.

Measures

We focussed on measures that capture the underpinning skills and characteristics that CYP likely require to fully access formal schooling. These included memory, attention, non-verbal ability, arithmetic skills, reading, language and communication, motor skills, neurodevelopmental characteristics, psychopathology, social functioning, and wellbeing. The specific measures differed for each dataset and developmental stage.

Our approach to selecting specific variables to include in the analysis was pragmatic and consisted of three steps: 1) we consulted CYP with lived experiences of SEND and their parents; 2) we searched the literature for indicators of SEND; 3) we identified variables in the datasets that captured the indicators identified through steps 1 and 2 and also maximised the comparability across datasets. The measures we selected are briefly summarised below.

Cognition

Data were collected by a mix of clinical assessments and parent-report questionnaires. We focussed on non-verbal ability, reading, maths, attention, short-term memory, literacy, decision making, and risk taking. We use these broad terms to describe the different aspects of cognition that we investigated but the exact cognitive function measured differs depending on each dataset (e.g., in some datasets 'reading' refers to non-word and word reading whereas in others it refers to word reading only). The majority of cognitive measures were standardised tools but some cohort specific novel measures were also used.

Language and Communication

Data were collected by a mix of clinical assessment and parent-report questionnaires. We used indicators of receptive, expressive, and pragmatic language, as well as intelligibility, based on standardised measures of language ability or screening questionnaires for language and communication difficulties. We

also used some cohort specific non-standardised measures of language and communication.

Motor Skills

Data were collected by a mix of clinical assessment and parent-report questionnaires. We focussed on fine motor skills.

Neurodevelopmental Characteristics

We relied on parent-report questionnaires. Specifically, we focussed on autistic characteristics as captured by screening questionnaires designed to identify CYP requiring further assessment for autism.

Social Functioning

Data were collected by self- and parent-report questionnaires. We focussed on peer problems, cooperation skills, and prosocial skills. All of the measures were captured by screening questionnaires intended to identify CYP requiring further assessment for a range of neurodevelopmental or psychiatric conditions.

Psychopathology

Data were collected by self- and parent-report questionnaires. We focussed on externalising psychopathology (e.g., conduct problems, hyperactivity), internalising psychopathology (e.g., symptoms of depression and anxiety), and transdiagnostic indicators of non-specific psychopathology (e.g., emotional regulation, self-regulation, inattention). All of the measures were screening questionnaires intended to identify CYP requiring further assessment for psychiatric conditions.

Wellbeing

Data were collected by self-report questionnaires administered in adolescence. We focussed on two aspects of wellbeing, specifically CYPs' self-esteem and subjective wellbeing.

Outcomes

We focussed on a range of outcomes. Our selection was driven by policy relevance and also guided by discussions with CYP with SEND and their parents during the co-production process. Specifically, we focussed on outcomes at different ages in three datasets: MCS - age 17 years; TEDS - age 21-26 years; ALSPAC - age 24-29 years. The outcomes we focussed on were:

- Education (e.g., GCSEs or Higher Education Qualifications)
- Employment (e.g., whether in employment)
- Finances (e.g., whether in receipt of state benefits)
- Antisocial behaviour (e.g., whether engaged in anti-social behaviour)
- Mental health (e.g., mental health diagnoses)

- Relationships (e.g., whether in a relationship)⁶

Genetic Data

In two of the datasets (ALSPAC, MCS) genetic data was available for both parents and children but only for a subset of families. Using information about common genetic differences between individuals, it is possible to generate a genetic propensity score (polygenic score) that captures an individual's broad propensity for a given outcome. In this study, we generated polygenic scores for three outcomes: 1) educational attainment (Okbay et al., 2022), 2) major depressive disorder (Adams et al., 2025), and 3) externalising problems (Karlsson Linnér et al., 2021). We selected these because the underlying score calculation came from large, robust studies and the measures broadly aligned with the three areas of development.

The availability of genetic information for both parents and children allowed us to calculate two sets of polygenic scores for each family. The first set was based on the genetic information shared between parents and their child (i.e., the genetic information that was passed down from parents to child), while the second captured the genetic information carried by parents but not passed down to their child. Splitting the genetic information in the way described enabled us to separate out genetic and environmental effects. For example, a parent who does not pass their high risk of depression down to their child *genetically* may nevertheless influence their child's likelihood of developing depression due to the influence of their own depressive symptoms on the way they interact with their child, i.e. an aspect of the child's *environment*.

Co-Production

We undertook a series of co-production activities at multiple stages of the project. We convened three sets of co-production groups. These groups met separately.

- Parents of CYP with SEND (n=8): CYPs' diagnoses included ADHD, Autism, Developmental Language Disorder, Specific Learning Difficulties (e.g., dyslexia), chromosomal differences (e.g., Down's Syndrome), demand avoidance, and social emotional and mental health difficulties.
- CYP with SEND (n=10): CYPs' diagnoses included ADHD, Autism, Dyslexia, Down's Syndrome, Prader-Willi Syndrome, and social emotional and mental health difficulties.
- Educational Professionals (n=8): Teachers, educational psychologists, special educational needs co-ordinators

We consulted the co-production groups at two stages of the project:

⁶ This is an example of our pragmatic use of co-production due to data limitations. CYP told us social relationships (e.g., friendships) were an extremely important outcome for them. Romantic relationships were the closest available measure that was consistently available across datasets.

1. Project Set-Up. We met with the parents and CYP groups to understand the shortcomings of the existing SEND types. We also shared a summary of the variables we intended to include in the analysis to ensure that they captured the strengths and challenges experienced by CYP with SEND.
2. Middle-to-End of Project. We met with all three groups to share the findings of work packages 1 and 2 to understand how they aligned with their lived experiences. We were specifically interested in whether the newly identified data-derived sub-groups fit with CYPs', parents' and teachers' conceptions of needs. To select the most appropriate data-derived sub-groups we presented a range of options. This guided our selection of which sub-groups to move forward with in the analysis.

We originally intended to explore the most inclusive and supportive language for discussing the genetic findings and their implications with the co-production groups. Given that findings for work package 3 showed minimal genetic influence on children's development, we decided not to do this.

Project Advisory Group

We convened a project advisory group. Full details of its composition and their involvement are outlined in Appendix A.

Dissemination Activities

We engaged in a range of dissemination activities to solicit feedback on our findings. These are outlined in Appendix B.

Statistical Analysis

For the first work package, exploring how developmental needs cluster, we used data from all four datasets and fitted network models (see Borsboom et al., 2021 for a primer). We fitted a total of 12 network models, one for each dataset and each developmental stage. We used network models to explore CYPs' needs not in isolation but as a set of connected needs that co-occur and potentially influence one another. In doing this, we mapped how various needs relate to each other and cluster in a transdiagnostic manner.

For work package 2, we used data from three datasets (ALSPAC, MCS, TEDS). We fitted latent class models to determine whether there are meaningful sub-groups of CYP based on patterns of social, emotional, and cognitive needs (see Sinha et al., 2021 for a primer). This data-driven approach follows an iterative process whereby an increasing number of sub-groups are generated which continue to split the sample further until the model fit becomes worse or the sub-groups become less meaningful. To explore co-occurrence of needs across all areas of development and the extent to which our identified sub-groups correspond to SEND labels used in schools, we generated 2-6 sub-groups for each dataset at each developmental stage and then chose one solution for each dataset and

developmental stage based on 1) consultation with CYP with SEND, their parents, and educational professionals, 2) interpretability of the sub-groups, 3) how well the models fit the data, and 4) comparability of sub-groups across datasets. We then visually compared these data-derived sub-groups to existing SEND types used in schools. Finally, we assessed whether the new data-derived sub-groups are better or worse at predicting outcomes compared to existing SEND labels using area under the curve analysis.

For work package 3, we added parent and child polygenic scores for educational attainment, major depressive disorder (a proxy for emotional difficulties), and externalising problems (a proxy for social difficulties) to the network models fitted for work package 1 for the ALSPAC and MCS datasets only.

Findings and Discussion

Work Package 1: Clusters of Need

A cluster is a group of needs that are strongly associated with each other across children in the sample. That is, they tend to co-occur more often with each other in the population than they do with other needs. This co-occurrence could be causal (e.g., one need could cause another need) or they could be related due to a third factor (e.g., both needs are caused by the same factor, e.g. persistent absence from school).

The results of our analysis for work package 1 were consistent across all four datasets. In early and middle childhood, CYPs' needs are clustered within two areas of development (cognition and language; social and emotional functioning) and in adolescence they are clustered within three areas of development (cognition and language; social functioning; emotional functioning).

Early and Middle Childhood

Cognition and Language. This area of development captures needs such as speaking to and understanding others, learning to read and write, solving mathematics problems, paying attention, remembering information for short periods of time, and overall problem-solving ability. These needs are strongly connected to one another, meaning CYP who have one of these needs are more likely to have another one of these needs.

These clusters are shown in Figure 1; thicker lines represent more co-occurrence. Take a CYP who has difficulty with speaking to others and understanding others. Because language needs are closely connected to reading and writing needs, that child is also likely to struggle to learn letter-sound relationships, understand what they read, or express their ideas clearly in writing. Over time, these difficulties might also affect their ability in mathematics, where understanding word problems depends on language comprehension.

Figure 1. A network model for middle childhood.

Note. The figure represents the ALSPAC dataset but a similar pattern was observed in the other datasets.

Social and Emotional Functioning. This area of development captures needs that shape how CYP manage themselves and relate to other people. It reflects how CYP regulate their behaviour and emotions, and how they connect and communicate with others. Again, these needs are closely linked, meaning that if a CYP has one of these needs they are more likely to have another one of these needs.

Again, referring to Figure 1, take a CYP who has difficulty understanding social cues and using language effectively in conversations. Because social communication is closely connected to peer relationships, this CYP is also likely to struggle to join in play, misread others' intentions, or say things that come across the wrong way. This might lead to peer problems, such as being left out or having frequent misunderstandings. Over time, repeated social difficulties might also contribute to emotional problems, such as feeling anxious, frustrated, or upset at school. In other words, the initial difficulties with social communication might ripple into peer relationships and emotional wellbeing.

Adolescence

Cognition and Language. In adolescence, needs associated with cognition and language continue to group together as they did in early and middle childhood. Needs associated with understanding and expressing complex ideas through language, reasoning and problem-solving, making decisions, and managing risk-taking are strongly connected to one another, meaning that adolescents who have one of these needs are more likely to have another.

For example, take a CYP who has difficulty with understanding and using words. Because understanding and using words is closely connected to short-term

memory, decision-making, risk-taking, mathematics, and non-verbal reasoning, this adolescent is also likely to struggle to remember steps in a maths problem, plan how to approach it, or weigh different solutions. As a result, they may fall behind in subjects like mathematics or science, where thinking, reasoning, and communicating ideas all matter.

Social Functioning. In adolescence, peers become central to daily life and social learning. Needs associated with understanding others and problems with friends cluster separately from emotional needs (see Figure 2). This is likely because peer interactions grow more complex and influential at this stage of life (Laursen & Veentra, 2021). The social functioning area of development captures needs that shape how adolescents connect and interact with others. It includes needs associated with understanding social cues, using language effectively in conversations, forming and maintaining friendships, and navigating social situations. These needs are closely linked. That means if a CYP has one of these needs they are more likely to have another.

Figure 2. A network model for adolescence.

Note. The figure represents the ALSPAC dataset but a similar pattern was observed in the other datasets.

For example, take a CYP who has difficulty reading social cues. Because social understanding is closely connected to communication, they are likely to misinterpret others' intentions, struggle to join in group discussions, or say things that are misunderstood. This might lead to peer problems, such as being excluded from activities or experiencing conflicts with friends.

Emotional Functioning. Adolescence is a period of physical, cognitive, and social change. Because emotions are usually more intense during adolescence

(Bailen et al., 2019), emotional needs form a distinct cluster, separate from social functioning (see Figure 2). This area of development captures needs that help adolescents manage their feelings and sense of self. These aspects are closely linked. That means if a CYP has one of these needs they are more likely to have another one of these needs.

For example, take a CYP who has low self-esteem. Because self-esteem is connected to overall wellbeing and mood, they are likely to feel anxious or sad more often, struggle to enjoy activities they once liked, or interpret social situations negatively. Over time, these challenges might contribute to symptoms of depression or persistent low mood.

Connections Across Areas of Development

Across both childhood and adolescence, the three areas of development we identified are not isolated. While each area of development groups needs that are more strongly connected to one another, the needs within an area of development also interact with needs in other areas of development. This means that needs in one area can influence, be influenced by, or simply co-occur with needs in other areas of development.

For example, a difficulty with spoken language (in the *Cognition and Language* area of development) can affect a CYPs' ability to communicate effectively with peers (in the *Social Functioning* area of development). Similarly, challenges in managing emotions might make it harder for a CYP to engage socially or make thoughtful decisions, creating connections between all three areas of development: *Emotional Functioning*, *Social Functioning* and *Cognition and Language*.

These connections across areas of development help explain why CYP often experience multiple needs. In early childhood, for example, difficulties with spoken language may ripple into cognition, learning, and social-emotional skills. By adolescence, as the areas of development become more differentiated, a CYP struggling with risk-taking or decision-making may also experience social conflicts or lower self-esteem. In other words, while areas of development highlight groups of tightly connected needs, the network models show that all needs are part of a broader interconnected system.

These findings have been published in a peer-reviewed academic journal (Deniz et al., 2026).

Work Package 2: Sub-groups of CYP with Similar Needs

We took the findings from work package 1 and used them to determine whether there are sub-groups of CYP who share similar needs within and across the three areas of development: cognition and language; social functioning; and emotional functioning. We did this in three datasets (ALSPAC, MCS, TEDS)⁷. The analytic model, latent class analysis, assigned each CYP into one sub-group. We

⁷ We initially included BCS in this analysis but were unable to derive meaningful sub-groups.

then interpreted the sub-groups based on how the average score for each sub-group compared to the rest of the sample. To compare the average score for screening measures we used the developers' guidelines on what score constitutes a risk requiring further assessment. For example, for a screening measure for psychiatric conditions scored between 0 to 10, if a score of 7 or above is considered high risk for psychiatric condition we considered a sub-group with a score of 7 or more as experiencing mental health difficulties. To compare the average score for standardised measures of functioning, we took the lowest 20% of scores as indicative of need. For example, for a measure of oral language where the scores on their own are meaningless (e.g., a score of 0 to 100) but become meaningful when compared to others (e.g., the lowest 20% have low language ability). The estimates for each type of need varied for each dataset and developmental stage (see Table 2).

Table 2. Proportions of CYP with Different Needs by Developmental Stage (Pooled Across Datasets)

	Early Childhood	Middle Childhood	Adolescence
Typically Developing	54-72%	67-75%	60-70%
Global Difficulties	<5%	2-15%	NA ⁸
Cognition and Language Difficulties	11-19%	18-22%	8-18%
Social, Emotional, and Behavioural Difficulties	8-31%	8-11%	5%
Social and Behavioural Difficulties	NA	NA	3-5%
Emotional Difficulties	NA	NA	8-28%

Note. A detailed breakdown of the sub-groups by dataset and developmental stage is shown in the Appendices C-E. The % are not intended to add up to 100% as they represent values from various datasets; they are intended to describe indicative ranges. NA indicates that this sub-group was not found in this developmental stage. For example, there were not enough CYP with emotional difficulties only in early childhood for it to warrant a separate sub-group. Instead, these CYP are likely included in the social, emotional, and behavioural difficulties sub-group.

There were some general patterns that we were able to interpret.

⁸ Birth cohort studies typically suffer from unequal attrition. CYP who are most disadvantaged are more likely to drop out from the research study compared to their peers. Therefore, the lack of a global difficulties sub-group in adolescence is likely to be indicative of this selective attrition, because CYP with the most severe needs likely dropped out of the study.

Typically Developing. At any one given point in time, most CYP can be considered typically developing. They do not experience difficulties with cognition or language, social functioning, or emotional functioning. The proportion of CYP who are typically developing varies depending on age.

Global Difficulties. Very few CYP show global difficulties (problems across multiple areas of development).

Cognitive and Language Difficulties. Some CYP experience difficulties with thinking, learning, and language. Cognitive and language difficulties are present in a notable minority across ages, peaking slightly in middle childhood, then remaining significant but somewhat lower in adolescence.

Social, Emotional, and Behavioural Difficulties. A small proportion of CYP experience difficulties with social skills, emotions and behaviour. These difficulties are more common in early childhood, then decline with age. By adolescence, only 5% of CYP show combined social, emotional and behavioural difficulties.

Social and Behavioural Difficulties. A small minority of adolescents experience difficulties with social skills and behaviour but not with their emotions. These difficulties tend not to occur in isolation in childhood (likely to be <5%). This makes sense given lots of social and behavioural difficulties are likely to be indicative of unmet needs.

Emotional Difficulties. A significant minority of adolescents show challenges in mood or wellbeing (e.g., anxiety, low self-esteem) without broader social, behavioural or cognitive difficulties. This aligns with adolescence being a period of heightened emotional vulnerability.

Summary Interpretation. Most CYP are typically developing throughout childhood and adolescence; they have no significant developmental needs. A small proportion experience global difficulties, affecting multiple areas of development, though this is relatively rare. Cognition and language difficulties are present in a notable minority at all ages, peaking slightly in middle childhood. Combined, social, emotional, and behavioural difficulties are more common in early childhood but decline with age, becoming less frequent by adolescence. In adolescence these difficulties tend to separate out and there are sub-groups of CYP with only emotional difficulties or only social and behavioural difficulties. This likely reflects the increased emotional vulnerability and importance of social relationships typical of this developmental stage.

Estimating the Level of Need in England

We sought to estimate the underlying level of developmental need in England based on the data-derived sub-groups that we generated. The datasets we used were sampled to be representative of England (except ALSPAC, which was representative of the Avon region). This allowed us to generate estimates of the underlying level of need without being biased by inequalities associated with SEND identification.

To estimate the level of need, we isolated all CYP for whom data was available at all three stages (early childhood, middle childhood, and adolescence).

Then we calculated in how many of the three stages each CYP was in a sub-group other than typically developing (i.e., one of the difficulty sub-groups). The results are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The number of stages at which children and young people experienced difficulties in each of the three datasets.

Across all three datasets, 35-44% of CYP did not experience any difficulties at any point during early childhood, middle childhood, or adolescence (blue segments in pie charts). Between 30-36% experienced difficulties at only *one stage* during early childhood, middle childhood, or adolescence (red segments in pie charts). Between 14-22% experienced any difficulties at *two stages* during early childhood, middle childhood, or adolescence (green segments in pie charts). Only a minority of CYP, 6-9%, experienced difficulties at *all three* stages (yellow segment in pie charts). We assumed that difficulties experienced at only one stage were transient or that the CYP received adequate support so the difficulties were resolved. Therefore, we summed those who experienced difficulties at two or three stages of development (i.e., we combined the green and yellow segments in the graphs) to estimate that the level of relatively persistent need in England is likely to be c.20%-30%.

This is almost certainly an underestimate given that those with the most severe needs are unlikely to be part of large research studies as they would be unable to complete the measures. Additionally, the most disadvantaged groups tend to be more likely to drop out of longitudinal studies and so are unlikely to have data at all three time points. Finally, we did not investigate physical and sensory needs so these are missing from the prevalence estimate; ~5% of CYP with SEND have a physical or sensory need.

Transitioning In and Out of Need

We mapped how CYP progressed through early childhood, middle childhood, and adolescence in terms of whether or not they had developmental needs. We did

this by collapsing all of the sub-groups that were not typically developing at each time point and then mapping what proportions moved into and out of the typically developing sub-group. We present the findings from the ALSPAC dataset in Figure 4. This pattern is similar in the other two datasets (see Appendices F and G).

Figure 4. Transitions In and Out of Need (ALSPAC)

As shown in Figure 2, of the CYP who have needs in early childhood, approximately half resolve these in middle childhood whilst others continue to struggle. Similarly, of the CYP who have needs in middle childhood approximately half resolve in adolescence whilst others continue to struggle. On the other hand, approximately 1 in 5 CYP who do not have needs in early childhood develop needs in middle childhood. Similarly, approximately 1 in 5 CYP who do not have needs in middle childhood develop needs in adolescence.

Figure 2 illustrates how CYPs transition between consecutive developmental stages, focussing only on transitions from the immediately preceding stage. Therefore, the figure should only be used to interpret transitions between early childhood and middle childhood or middle childhood to adolescence. It cannot be used to map transitions from early childhood through middle childhood to adolescence.

Correspondence of Sub-Groups of CYP with Similar Needs with SEND types

We mapped whether the sub-groups of CYP with similar needs, derived from the data, correspond to those CYP’s SEND types. Parents, and in some cases teachers, were asked if the CYP had a SEND identified in school and, if so, what it was. This was recorded differently for each dataset, but some broad SEND types were captured consistently (see Appendices C-E).

Identification of SEND. Across all datasets and ages, SEND identification consistently aligns closely with the sub-groups derived from the data. CYP in the typically developing sub-groups show the lowest levels of SEND identification, reflecting the fact that only a small proportion of CYP receive SEND support despite otherwise typical development. As we would expect, the sub-groups with global difficulties show the highest levels of SEND identification. Rates of SEND identification are also higher in the cognitive and language difficulties sub-groups than the typically developing sub-groups, indicating that schools usually recognise these needs. Notably, the social, emotional, and behavioural difficulties sub-groups show levels of SEND identification comparable to or exceeding the cognitive and language sub-groups, demonstrating that social, emotional, and behavioural difficulties frequently trigger SEND support. In adolescence, the sub-groups with emotional difficulties show moderately elevated levels of SEND identification compared to the typically developing group, suggesting that emotional difficulties alone are less likely to activate SEND support. Taken together, these patterns show that schools' SEND identification broadly mirrors whether or not a CYP has needs, with higher recognition in groups showing more complex or wide-ranging needs.

Importantly, although SEND identification was higher in all sub-groups other than the typically developing sub-group, not all CYP within these sub-groups had been identified with SEND at school. Even in sub-groups characterised by clear cognitive, language, behavioural, or global difficulties, a substantial proportion of CYP had not been identified as having SEND. There could be for a number of reasons. Transient difficulties that are relatively easily resolved may not trigger a formal SEND identification. The findings could also reflect previously reported inconsistencies and inequalities in SEND identification (Hutchinson et al, 2025), indicating that some CYP with needs remain unidentified within the education system.

Overlap between SEND Types and Data-Derived Sub-Groups. We also looked at the specific SEND types of the CYP within each of the data-derived subgroups. Across all three datasets (see Appendices C-E), CYP in every non-typically developing sub-group show a mix of SEND types. For example, learning-related SEND types appear not only in the cognitive and language sub-groups but also in the social, emotional, and behavioural sub-groups; ASD and ADHD are not confined to behaviourally defined groups; and SEMH needs are recorded across multiple sub-groups, particularly in adolescence. This lack of correspondence between SEND types and data-derived sub-groups reiterates that CYPs' needs are complex and that the current SEND types fail to capture them, potentially obscuring broader patterns of need and leading to inconsistent identification. The evidence across datasets therefore supports our argument that the existing SEND types do not sufficiently reflect how CYPs' needs actually co-occur, limiting their usefulness for supporting CYP with SEND.

Predicting Outcomes using Sub-Groups

We used the data-derived sub-groups to predict outcomes post compulsory education and during young adulthood. We did this to determine whether the pattern or types of needs CYP experience in childhood and adolescence are associated with differing patterns of outcomes later in life. The outcomes we were interested in were education (e.g., GCSEs or higher education qualifications), employment (e.g., whether in employment), finances (e.g., whether in receipt of state benefits), anti-social behaviour (e.g., whether engaged in anti-social behaviour), mental health (e.g., mental health diagnoses), and relationships (e.g., whether in a relationship). We compared each sub-group at each time point with every other sub-group at the same time point. These comparisons are presented in Appendices H-M and interpreted below.

Outcomes in the Late Teens. CYP in any of the difficulty sub-groups in childhood and/or adolescence were less likely to have achieved 5+ GCSE passes and be in any kind of employment, and more likely to have a mental health diagnosis at age 17 years compared to those in the typically developing sub-groups⁹. There were few and inconsistent differences in terms of anti-social behaviour, health service use, and relationships.

Outcomes in the Early to Mid-Twenties. CYP in any of the difficulty sub-groups in childhood and/or adolescence were 1) less likely to have a university degree, 2) less likely to be employed, 3) more likely to be in receipt of state benefits, 4) more likely to engage in anti-social behaviour, and 5) more likely to have a mental health diagnosis between the ages of 21 and 26 years than those in the typically developing sub-groups. These effects were more pronounced for those who experienced difficulties in middle childhood and/or adolescence. There were few and inconsistent differences in terms of health service use and relationships.

Outcomes in the Mid to Late Twenties. CYP in any of the difficulty sub-groups in childhood and/or adolescence were 1) less likely to have a university degree, 2) less likely to be employed, 3) more likely to be in receipt of state benefits, and 4) less likely to be in a relationship between the ages of 24 and 29 years. These effects were more pronounced for those who experienced difficulties in middle childhood and/or adolescence. There were few and inconsistent differences in terms of anti-social behaviour, mental health diagnosis, and health service use.

Summary of Outcomes. Regardless of which age we looked at between 17 and 29 years, CYP who were in one of our data-derived difficulties sub-groups in childhood or adolescence tended to do worse in terms of educational attainment and employment than their typically-developing peers. When they became entitled to state benefits, they were more likely to receive them. They also tended to do worse

⁹ There were a few exceptions to this, which are shown in the appendices.

in terms of anti-social behaviour, mental health, and relationships, though these effects were not as consistent.

Sub-Groups of Needs vs SEND types Predicting Outcomes

We were also interested in whether our data-derived sub-groups, which describe CYPs' cognitive, language, social, and emotional functioning between ages 3-14, could predict outcomes at 17-29 years old more accurately than existing SEND types. For each CYP, we created two binary variables. The first was whether or not they had any SEND (i.e., any one of the SEND types, as reported by parents/teachers, was coded as yes, otherwise they were coded as no). The second was whether or not they were in any one of the data-derived difficulty sub-groups (i.e., any one of the difficulty sub-groups at any of the three developmental stages was coded as yes, otherwise they were coded as no)

When predicting outcomes, 50% prediction can be considered a chance prediction. Anything more than 50% is considered prediction better than chance. For all three datasets, the data-derived sub-groups predicted outcomes with accuracy of 53-73%, depending on the outcome and dataset. The SEND types predicted outcomes with accuracy of 53-71%, again depending on the outcome and dataset (see Appendix N).

For approximately half of the outcomes, there was no difference in the prediction accuracy of the data-derived sub-groups and the SEND types. For the other half, the data-derived sub-groups were better at predicting outcomes than the SEND types. SEND types were only better than the data-derived sub-groups at predicting GCSE outcomes. However, most differences in prediction accuracy were very small (mostly <5%)¹⁰.

While existing SEND types slightly outperform data-derived sub-groups in predicting GCSE attainment, this adds limited practical value because prior attainment already provides strong predictive information. By contrast, our data-derived sub-groups better predict longer-term and broader outcomes (e.g., mental health, anti-social behaviour, reliance on state benefits, university education). For these longer-term and broader outcomes, SEND type labels are less informative than our data-derived sub-groups. For outcomes where both approaches perform equally, such as employment, health service use, and relationships, the sub-groups offer no loss of accuracy.

Taking these findings together, we conclude that recording CYPs' needs as a full profile of strengths and challenges would be a good replacement for existing SEND types for providing insight for outcomes that matter to CYP in the longer term and to government policy objectives.

¹⁰ The two exceptions were University degree at age 21-26 (8% better prediction for data-derived sub-groups) and in receipt of state benefits at age 21-25 (6% better prediction for data-derived sub-groups)

Work Package 3: Genetic and Environmental Influences

In the final part of the project we sought to understand how CYP's strengths and challenges in early childhood, middle childhood, and adolescence are shaped by their genetics and environments. We hoped that disentangling these influences would allow us to determine who or what should be the target for early intervention.

Genetics influence chances, they do not determine outcomes. Just as a challenging family background increases the chances of poor educational outcomes but not all CYP from challenging family backgrounds have poor educational outcomes, a low genetic tendency for education increases the chances of poor educational outcomes but does not make them a certainty. The environment is important too.

Importantly, genetics and environments are interdependent. CYP inherit 50% of their genetic differences from each parent (shared genetic component), meaning parents pass on both risk and resilience. At the same time, parental genetics (irrespective of whether they are passed on to their children) shape the environment in which CYP grow up (e.g., parents with high genetic propensity for education might create a positive home learning environment with lots of books and/or have higher paid jobs meaning they have higher a socioeconomic status).

We used genetic data to understand the role of genes and the environment in shaping CYPs' strengths and challenges. In two datasets (ALSPAC and MCS), we calculated two sets of genetic scores, known as polygenic scores: 1) CYPs' polygenic scores for educational attainment, emotional difficulties, and behavioural difficulties that were transmitted from their parents; and 2) parents' polygenic scores for educational attainment, emotional difficulties, and behavioural difficulties that were not transmitted to their child. We selected these because the underlying score calculation came from large, robust studies and the measures they considered were informative for our models; they are also the most closely related to the three areas of development. The CYP polygenic scores were used as an indicator of the CYPs' direct genetic tendency to develop various needs and the parents' polygenic scores were used an indicator of the environment the parents create¹¹. We took these scores and added them to the network models that we fitted in work package 1; this allowed us to test how genetics and environments are related to CYP development.

Early Childhood. In early childhood, genetic influences were very small. When we ranked every variable in the models by how strongly it was connected to the others, the CYPs' polygenic scores and the parents' polygenic scores consistently came out at the very bottom. What stood out instead was how strongly CYPs' early needs relate to one another. Needs linked to language, thinking, attention, self-control, and social-emotional functioning shape each other far more than genetics shapes any of them at this age.

¹¹ The logic here is that if the genetic variants that are associated with positive educational outcomes are present in the parent and not passed down to the child, then the reason these would be associated with the child's outcomes is because the parents' genetic tendencies help them to shape the environment they create, which then impacts upon the child's outcomes.

Middle Childhood. In middle childhood, we see clearer signs that genetics is beginning to matter, but the size of these effects is still small compared with CYPs' needs. CYPs' own genetic propensities show the strongest links with 'cognition and language' needs like reading, maths, reasoning, memory, and expressive language. This aligns with evidence that the heritability of cognitive functioning (the extent to which differences in cognitive functioning between CYP can be explained by genetic differences) increases at this age. That is, the differences between CYP in cognitive functioning in early childhood are mostly explained by their environments whereas in middle childhood they are mostly explained by genetic differences (Davis et al., 2009). This suggests that CYPs' needs are becoming more closely linked to their genetic propensities in middle childhood. By middle childhood CYPs' needs in the area of 'cognition and language' might start to reflect more stable, longer-term differences rather than the short-term fluctuations that are common earlier in childhood. Needs in the 'social and emotional' area of development, however, continue to be shaped mainly by CYPs' needs and environments, with only very small genetic links. The overall pattern is one where CYPs' needs remain the main drivers of their development, and genetics is beginning to contribute but does not dominate.

When we ranked every variable in the model to see which influences were most strongly connected to CYP's needs, CYPs' own genetic propensities appeared towards the lower end of the rankings. They were stronger than parents' genetic propensities, but still much weaker than almost all needs in 'cognition and language' and 'social and emotional' areas of development. Parents' polygenic scores were near the very bottom, showing only small and selective links to CYPs' development. These rankings indicate that CYPs' genetic propensities are starting to play a noticeable, but still modest, role in shaping their needs in middle childhood, while parents exert only a very minor influence on their children's development through the environments they create.

Adolescence. In adolescence, genetics continues to matter, and more so than middle childhood, but the size of these effects is still small compared with CYPs' needs. CYPs' own genetic propensities show their strongest links with 'cognition and language', and with some aspects of 'social functioning', but these links remain modest. The strongest influences on CYPs' development in adolescence continue to be their own needs; expressive language, self-esteem, conduct problems, hyperactivity, wellbeing, and emotional difficulties sit at the very top of the influence rankings in both datasets. This pattern suggests that by adolescence, like middle childhood, CYPs' needs reflect stable, longer-term differences between individuals, but these differences are still shaped far more by their needs than by their genetic scores.

When we ranked every variable in the model to see which influences were most strongly connected to CYPs' development, CYPs' own genetic propensities appeared toward the lower end of the rankings. They were stronger than parents' genetic propensities, but still much weaker than almost all needs in both the 'cognition and language' and 'social and emotional' areas of development. Parents'

genetic scores were near the very bottom, showing only very small and selective links to adolescents' development. These rankings indicate that, while CYP's genetic propensities play a noticeable but modest role in shaping their needs in adolescence, parents continue to exert only a very minor influence on their children's development through the environments they create.

Interpretation across Developmental Stages

In early childhood, CYPs' needs show very few consistent links to underlying genetic tendencies, and neither CYPs' nor parents' genetic inclinations are meaningfully associated with early cognitive and language skills or social-emotional functioning. At this stage, development is driven almost entirely by children's emerging needs. For example, how they explore, communicate, regulate their emotions, and interact with others. These early needs are fluid and changeable, and the wider environments children experience likely play a much larger role than their own genetics or the environments created by parents influenced by their own genetic propensities. We speculate a few possible explanations for the lack of genetic effects.

One explanation is that many of the environmental influences that are important in early childhood development might not be driven by parents' genetics. Parent polygenic scores capture only those aspects of the home environments that are shaped by parents' genetically influenced characteristics, but they do not reflect aspects of the home environment that are independent of these genetic propensities. These may include responses to external guidance or constraints, such as following advice from health visitors, adhering to guidance from early years settings or public health recommendations, or adapting parenting practices in response to a child's illness or developmental needs. Such influences may play a particularly important role in shaping development in early childhood; this is a speculation and needs to be tested specifically in future work.

Another possible explanation is that polygenic scores have limited utility. While they provide a useful way of summarising genetic differences, they capture only a small proportion of the genetic influences on complex developmental needs and are therefore an incomplete measure of genetic influence. This is often referred to as 'missing heritability'; the gap between the likely true genetic influence and the estimates obtained using polygenic scores. In addition, our understanding of how genetic differences relate to specific developmental needs is still evolving. As a result, polygenic scores can be imprecise or 'noisy' and may not fully reflect the true contribution of genetics.

This limitation may matter more in early childhood than later during development because genetic influences are harder to detect at this stage. Young children's skills and behaviours are still developing and can change quickly from day to day, making them less consistent and harder to measure. In addition, polygenic scores are usually based on studies of older children or adults, so they may not match as well with how abilities show up in very young children. As children grow older and their skills become more stable, these genetic influences become easier to observe, and polygenic scores tend to be more informative.

Polygenic scores are also shaped by the data and populations from which they are derived, meaning they may not capture all relevant genetic variation equally well across individuals or contexts. Taken together, these limitations mean that the relatively small genetic effects observed in our analyses may partly reflect measurement constraints, rather than the absence of meaningful genetic influence on CYPs' development.

We found that by middle childhood, CYPs' genetic tendencies begin to show through more clearly, especially in influencing cognitive and language needs relating to reading, reasoning, memory, and expressive language. Parents' influence via the environments they create is modest. This is the stage where CYPs' strengths and challenges start to stabilise, and where the environments they experience begin to reflect these emerging patterns; CYP who excel in 'cognitive and language' may be given more advanced materials, for example, while those with needs in this area might be given more structured support. Because these patterns are becoming clearer, universal screening for a broad range of needs followed by targeted support is likely to build on established strengths in cognition and language and address specific needs before they become entrenched.

By adolescence, CYPs' established genetic tendencies shape how they respond to teaching, how they manage their emotions, and how they navigate school and social life. Parents' influence remains small, and it is adolescents' own well-established patterns of strengths and challenges across all three areas of development that account for most of the differences between CYP at this stage. For policy, this means young people require flexible support that recognises their more settled profiles and helps them succeed across a wider range of routes. As CYPs' genetic tendencies become more visible and their strengths and challenges more established, the education system needs to offer a genuine diversification of pathways. Offering a wider range of academic, vocational, creative, and technical routes will allow young people to progress in ways that align with their emerging skills and needs.

Together, these findings point to a system where universal screening at two points in childhood, at the beginning of primary school and mid-primary school, is likely to have the widest impact; it will ensure early and accurate identification and allow for appropriate support to be put in place. Screening for social and emotional needs should be undertaken around the beginning of secondary school.

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Appendices

Appendix A. Advisory Group

We convened a project advisory group comprised of the following:

- Professor Sophie von Stumm, University of York
- Stephen Kingdom & Cath Lunt, Disabled Children's Partnership
- Tom McBride, Early Intervention Foundation
- Wendy Van Rikswijk, Department of Education
- Professor Jenny Gibson, University of Cambridge
- Dr Jessie Baldwin, University College London
- Professor Charles Hulme, Oxford Brookes University
- Alice Reeves, Nuffield Foundation

We formally met with the advisory group on two occasions during the project.

- Project Set-Up. We presented our proposal for the project including research questions, datasets, variables, and analytics methods. We also discussed the learnings from the co-production group based on the discussions.
- Mid Project. We shared our findings from work package 1 and work package 2 with the advisory group via an online meeting. We discussed the learnings from the co-production groups and discussed the possible implications of the findings. We sought feedback on the best routes to publication.

Following these advisory group meetings, we shared a draft of the first academic paper (findings from work package 1), for comment by email. Once we have written the two other academic papers, we will share for comment by email with the advisory group.

We also approached advisory group members, ad-hoc, by email with specific questions about the project that aligned with their expertise.

Appendix B: Dissemination Activities and Outputs

Academic Department Presentations

The findings from work packages 1 and 2 were discussed at a number of departmental seminars at research institutes across England and in Europe. The audiences consisted of academics in the field of Education, Psychology, Allied Health Professionals, and Psychiatry. Specifically the findings were presented at Bradford Institute for Health Research, Yorkshire Youth Mental Health Forum, University of Manchester, University of Oxford, University of York, University of Bath, Institut national d'études démographiques (France), Université PSL (France), and University of Bradford.

Academic Conferences

The findings from work packages 1 and 2 were presented at two academic conferences:

1. British Psychological Society, Developmental Section
2. International Conference on Child and Adolescent Psychopathology

Science Communication

The findings from work package 2 were discussed in a feature length episode of the [Mind the Kids Podcast](#). The episode has been viewed over 70,000 times on YouTube and streamed approximately 1,000 times across major streaming platforms (e.g., Apple Podcasts, Spotify etc.).

Policy Engagement

The findings of work packages 1 and 2 were shared with policy makers at the Department for Education in two ways:

1. We delivered an online research seminar at the Department for Education, which was attended by ~50 policy makers/analysts/civil servants.
2. We discussed the findings at a roundtable at the Department for Education, which was attended by ~15 civil servants, policy makers, and school leaders.

Outputs

To date, we have produced two outputs (more are planned):

1. The findings from work package 1 have been published for publication in the journal *Developmental Science*. [The paper is available online.](#)
2. A [policy brief](#) covering the findings from work packages 1 and 2 was produced, made available online, and shared with relevant stakeholders. To date, this has been viewed 114 times and downloaded 61 times.

Appendix C. Correspondence of Sub-Groups to School Identified Needs (ALSPAC Dataset)

Sub-Groups in Early Childhood (ALSPAC)

Sub-Groups in Middle Childhood (ALSPAC)

Sub-Groups in Adolescence (ALSPAC)

Appendix D. Correspondence of Sub-Groups to School Identified Needs (MCS Dataset)

Sub-Groups in Early Childhood (MCS)

Sub-Groups in Middle Childhood (MCS)

Sub-Groups in Adolescence (MCS)

Appendix E. Correspondence of Sub-Groups to School Identified Needs (TEDS Dataset)

Sub-Groups in Early Childhood (TEDS)

Sub-Groups in Middle Childhood (TEDS)

Sub-Groups in Adolescence (TEDS)

Appendix F. Transitions In and Out of Need (MCS)

Appendix G. Transitions In and Out of Need (TEDS)

Appendix H. Education and Employment Outcomes (Age 17 years)

Note. Dots show the estimated effect and lines (“tails”) show uncertainty. The vertical dashed line marks no difference. Points to the right mean more likely in the target group; to the left mean less likely, compared with the comparison group. The comparison group is the one listed on the left (e.g., No SEND vs SEN, No SEND is the comparison group). If a line crosses the centre, it suggests that the groups do not differ on the outcome.

Appendix I. Social, Emotional, and Health Outcomes (Age 17 years)

Appendix J. Education, Employment, and Finance Outcomes (Age 21-26 years)

Appendix K. Social, Emotional, and Health Outcomes (Age 21-26 years)

Appendix L. Education, Employment, and Finance Outcomes (Age 24-29 years)

Appendix M. Social, Emotional, and Health Outcomes (Age 24-29 years)

Appendix N. Comparison of Data-Derived Sub-Groups to Existing SEND Label

Age (years)	Outcome	Data Sub-Groups	SEND Types	chi2	Which is better?
17	5+ GCSEs	69%	71%	11.89***	SEND Labels
17	Employment	65%	65%	0.01	Tie
17	Ant-Social Behaviour	65%	64%	4.77*	Sub-Groups
17	Mental Health Diagnosis	73%	68%	31.44***	Sub-Groups
17	Health Service Use	59%	59%	1.37	Tie
17	Relationship	64%	64%	0.01	Tie
21-26	University Degree	64%	56%	38.07***	Sub-Groups
21-26	Employed	54%	53%	0.10	Tie
21-26	State Benefits	64%	58%	5.36*	Sub-Groups
21-26	Anti-Social Behaviour	65%	61%	4.64*	Sub-Groups
21-26	Mental Health Diagnosis	62%	59%	6.27*	Sub-Groups
21-26	Health Service Use	61%	61%	0.10	Tie
21-26	Relationship	53%	53%	0.01	Tie
24-29	University Degree	68%	68%	4.31*	Sub-Groups
24-29	Employed	59%	59%	0.31	Tie
24-29	State Benefits	69%	69%	0.77	Tie
24-29	Anti-Social Behaviour	59%	58%	0.79	Tie
24-29	Mental Health Diagnosis	61%	59%	10.94***	Sub-Groups
24-29	Health Service Use	67%	67%	0.00	Tie
24-29	Relationship	56%	56%	0.02	Tie

*p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001

**Department of
Psychology**